

Real-time detection of gas-phase organohalogenes from aqueous photochemistry using Orbitrap Mass Spectrometry

Supporting Information

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Experimental Methods

Reagents: sodium chloride (Sigma-Aldrich, 99+%); sodium bromide (Sigma-Aldrich, 99+%); sodium iodide (Sigma-Aldrich, 99+%); 1-octanol (Sigma Aldrich, 99%); 4-benzoylbenzoic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%); 1-Bromopinacolone (Alfa Aesar, 97%,) and 1,5-diodopentane (Alfa Aesar, 97%,).

APCI-HRMS:

Figure S1. (a) original APCI source, (b) modified APCI source.

Figure S2. Mass spectrum of the analysis of 1-Bromopinacolone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{BrO}$) in negative mode. The two mass correspond to isotope of brome.

Figure S3. Mass spectrum of the analysis of 1,5-diiodopentane ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{I}_2$) in negative mode.

Figure S4. Mass spectrum of the analysis of 1-Bromopinacolone ($C_6H_{11}BrO$) in positive mode.

Figure S5. Mass spectrum of the analysis of 1,5-diiodopentane ($C_5H_{10}I_2$) in positive mode.

Figure S6. Experimental setup for measuring online gas-phase products upon irradiation with Orbitrap mass spectrometer. A Xenon lamp with a pyrex filter is used to simulate solar irradiation ($\lambda > 290 \text{ nm}$) at the air/water interface. Depending on the experiment, the solution contains sea-salt halides, a photosensitizer, a surfactant.

Figure S7. Absolute irradiance as function of wavelength for the actinic solar spectrum (calculated using the Tropospheric Ultraviolet and Visible (TUV) Radiation Model version 5.2; http://cprm.acom.ucar.edu/Models/TUV/Interactive_TUV) and the xenon lamp with Pyrex filter used for irradiation of the biofilm samples

Figure S8. APCI-HRMS results in negative mode from a typical irradiation experiment. The intensities of Br^- signals in the gas phase are plotted as a function of time

Figure S9. APCI-HRMS results from a typical irradiation experiment. The intensities of $C_{12}H_{19}ClO_2^+$ (a) signals and $C_{13}H_{19}BrO_2^+$ (b) in positive mode in the gas phase are plotted as a function of time.

Scheme S1: Proposed Mechanism for Photochemical Reactions in the Presence of Photosensitizer and Halides.

The first step of the proposed mechanism (Scheme-S1) is the known formation of the photosensitizer triplet state under irradiation. From this energetic state, the photosensitizer can then initiate charge exchange reactions with the halides, and especially with the most reactive one i.e., iodide. This will produce atomic iodine, which in turn will initiate various known chain reactions producing mixed halogenated radical anions and atomic halogens¹⁻⁴. Their reactivity is such that they may react with the surrounding organic matter, i.e., the photosensitizer itself in this case, producing volatile halogenated products.

As shown in Scheme 1, multiple oxidation steps are suggested to explain the formation of the products detected by (+)-APCI-HRMS. The cleavage of a C-R bond adjacent to the carbonyl function is possible from this excited state, leading to the formation of various radicals (e.g., OH radical, phenylic radicals **1** and **2** in Scheme 1). From here, various radical-radical reactions may take place. For instance, the reaction between chlorine atoms and benzenylic radicals **1** can explain the formation of C₇H₅ClO. The chlorine atoms, which are necessary for this halogenation reaction, are produced from charge-transfer reactions of remaining triplet-state 4-BBA molecules and chloride ions in solution. Other products are likely to be produced via a phenyl radical-intermediate, forming the alkoxy radical **3** after reaction with H₂O.⁵ The ring opening of molecule **3** occurs in presence of O₂ and leads to an intermediary molecule **4** then O is removed thanks to the presence of radicals (e.g., halides radicals, OH radicals). Finally, butene-1,4-dial and one aldehyde radical are formed from this last radical **4**.⁶ Several molecules are produced from **5** (butene-1,4-dial) after decarboxylation by photo-Kolbe mechanism, H-abstraction and radical's addition, such as: C₁₀H₉ClO, C₃H₃BrO, C₃H₅IO and C₉H₇ClO. Radical **6** conducts to form C₈H₇ClO and C₈H₇BrO after halide radicals' addition.⁷ Supported by the

detection of Br⁻ and I⁻ fragment ions, and in combination with the observed halogenated products given in Table 1, the mechanism presented here is consistent with a complex free-radical chemistry in the bulk solution, which is readily initiated by CDOM proxies upon irradiation.

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